

1 **Cox family enzymes are therapeutic targets in ulcerative colitis.**

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6 Each of the following cytochrome oxidase enzymes were induced and highly activated in the blood of
7 humans with ulcerative colitis.

- 8 a. Cox5b
- 9 b. Cox6a1
- 10 c. Cox7a2
- 11 d. Cox5b1
- 12 e. Cox8a
- 13 f. Cox14
- 14 g. Cox17
- 15 h. Cox20 was repressed (silenced) instead.

16 Citations

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